

A Comprehensive Survey of Electrical Signal supported Condition Monitoring Methodology for Detecting with Diagnosing Faults in Induction Motor

Rima Mahendrabhai Pujara^{*1}, Dr. Chiragkumar Parekh^{#2} & Dr. Riaz Kurbanali Israni^{#3}

^{*1}Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Technology, R K University, Gujarat

^{#2}Associate Professor, Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Technology, R K University, Gujarat &

^{#3}Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical Engineering, Faculty of Technology, R K University, Gujarat

Abstract — The seamless and efficient process of 3 phase induction motor (IM) is crucial for modern industries. This paper begins by reviewing traditional time-domain and frequency-domain analyses of trembling and current signature used toward diagnose various IM faults, using data from dissimilar faulty IMs in a laboratory setting. It then discusses the benefits and challenges of these conventional methods. Following this, the paper summarizes current research and advancements in signal-based automation techniques for condition monitoring, focusing on detecting and diagnosing different electrical and mechanical faults in IMs. Recently, artificial intelligence (AI) techniques have been increasingly utilized for IM and other machinery fault diagnosis. The paper provides a detailed review of advancements in AI-based fault analysis, including trendy methods, which are being integrated with traditional monitoring approaches. The focus is primarily on techniques developed in the past decade. The review covers system signals, conventional and advanced signal processing methodologies, and emphasizes selecting effective arithmetical features, AI methods, & associated teaching and testing strategies for IM fault diagnostics. In addition, the paper talk about current advancement, identifies research gaps, and explores outlook directions in IM fault monitoring and analysis.

Keywords — Artificial Intelligence, Condition Monitoring, Electrical Current Signal, Fault Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Induction motors (IMs) are essential to the industrial sector, playing a pivotal role in mechanical power generation, manufacturing, and transportation. They are widely used in applications such as pumps, compressors, blowers, fans, machine tools, cranes, conveyors, and electric vehicles. Motors, particularly induction motors, account for over 50% of the global electrical energy consumption, with about 60% of industrial electricity used by these motors. The increasing adoption of IMs in various industries is driven by their affordability, durability, high power-to-weight ratio, and versatility across diverse operational environments [1].

Ensuring the dependability and accessibility of induction motors (IMs) is crucial for maintaining uninterrupted and efficient industrial operations. However, IMs face a variety of unavoidable stresses mechanical, thermal, electrical, and environmental—during their operation. These stresses can result from factors such as external load fluctuations, power supply inconsistencies, excessive heat, insufficient lubrication, poor sealing, dusty environments, manufacturing defects, and natural aging. Such conditions can cause unexpected faults in various motor components [1]. These faults can easily go unnoticed in their early stages, which may result in catastrophic motor failure, significant financial losses from process shutdowns, and potentially severe damages.

To reduce the risk of shattering motor failure, early recognition and analysis of faults in IM components are crucial [2]. Condition monitoring allows for continuous assessment of these components throughout their operational life. By diagnosing faults early, potential failures can be anticipated, enabling condition-based maintenance and reducing downtime [2].

II. VARIOUS TYPES OF FAULTS IN INDUCTION MOTORS

The IM is made up of 3 key mechanisms: the stator, rotor, and bearings. Failures in an IM can occur due to damage in any of these components or their subcomponents. IM faults are generally classified into two categories: electrical and mechanical, as shown in the figure below.

Fig. 1 Meticulous outlook of an IM

The anticipated failure rates for induction motor (IM) components are as follows: (i) Bearing damage: 41–42%, (ii) Stator winding damage: 28–36%, (iii) Rotor-related damage: 8–9%, and (iv) Other types of damage: 14–28%. Combined, bearings and stator windings contribute to at least 69% of all motor faults [3].

While rotor and shaft failures are relatively rare, bearing damage frequently results from factors such as an eccentric rotor, misaligned or unbalanced shafts, and occasionally, winding failures due to defective rotors [3]. Most winding failures stem from an unbalanced power supply. When considering rotor-related faults (such as broken rotor bars, misalignment, and imbalance) along with other induction motor (IM) issues like phase unbalance and single phasing, over 90% of all fault modes are accounted for the same.

A. Mechanical type faults in IM:

Approximately 50 to 60% of IM breakdowns are attributed to mechanical type faults. The paper describes a range of types of mechanical error in depth.

A. 1 Bearing fault:

The majority IM use ball or roller bearings, which consist of rolling elements, an outer race, an inner race, and a cage. Common causes of bearing failures include high rotor vibrations from excessive load torque, improper installation, and lubrication deterioration due to shaft voltage, heat transfer, friction, and

contamination [3] [4]. Bearing faults can lead to rotor eccentricity, unbalanced magnetic pull (UMP), and excessive vibration, ultimately causing rotor bar failures and premature motor breakdowns.

Fig. 2 Different categories of faults in induction motor [3]

A. 2 Rotor related fault:

In the defect-free induction motor (IM), the rotor remains centrally aligned with the stator, maintaining a constant air gap between them. However, if the rotor's axis shifts, causing an uneven air gap, this condition is known as air-gap eccentricity, a common fault in IMs. Eccentricity can be static, where the minimum radial air gap remains fixed [4].

Fig. 3 The hard replica of a bearing fault in the IM

In contrast, dynamic eccentricity involves the least air-gap position rotating with the rotor. Significant strangeness can cause substantial radial forces, especially at high speeds, leading to rubbing between the stator and rotor, which can damage one or both components. Peculiarity may arise from various issues, including

misalignment during the commissioning stage, mis-alignment between the motor shaft & load shaft, incorrect bearing installation, rotor imbalance, bearing wear, and mechanical resonance when passing during serious speeds.

A. 2. 1 Rotor misalignment:

Rotor misalignment (MR) can be parallel, angular, or a combination of both. Parallel misalignment occurs when the air gap between the stator and rotor remains fixed, often due to improper positioning during setup. Angular misalignment happens when the rotor's center doesn't align with its rotational axis, causing the air gap to rotate with the rotor, often due to a bent shaft, imbalance, or bearing wear. Induction motors (IMs) allow up to 10% air gap strangeness [5]. Excessive MR can create unbalanced forces, leading to rotor-to-stator rubbing, core damage, and potential IM failure.

A. 2. 2 Bowed rotor:

The bowed rotor (BR) and bent rotor are similar phenomena. The key difference is that bowed rotor deformation is measurable within the machine housing or on mounted bearings due to the rotor's static weight, while bent rotor deformation is observable outside the machine, even without mounting, and is caused by permanent rotor deformation [5] [6].

Fig. 4 Air gap eccentricities in the IM in rotor motion (a) normal motor (b) motor through static eccentricity (c) motor through dynamic eccentricity

This deformation causes dynamic air-gap eccentricity. Bowed rotor deformation results from factors like local rubbing, permanent bowing due to expansion and yielding, creep from the rotor's weight when stationary, and residual stresses [6]. Ultimately, this can lead to rotor misalignment, rotor-to-stator rubbing, and motor damage.

B. Electrical faults in induction motors:

About 35-40% of IM failures are due to electrical issues. Here are some common electrical faults linked to these failures.

B. 1 Stator winding fault:

SWFs can occur from various faults, including turn-to-turn, coil-to-coil, phase-to-phase, or phase-to-ground, often due to undetected turn-to-turn defects from insulation failure. Causes include thermal aging, excessive heating, electrical imbalances, mechanical impacts, vibration, installation errors, or oil contamination, potentially leading to circuit failures and total machine breakdown [7].

The non-uniform magnetic field in induction motor air gaps can cause unbalanced voltages and currents, resulting in mechanical vibration and increased torque pulsation.

Fig. 5 A range of probable faults in the stator winding of an IM

B.2 Broken rotor bar faults:

Despite the robust construction of squirrel cage induction motor rotors, broken rotor bars (BRBs) are a common issue, often caused by fluctuating loads, direct online starting, frequent high-voltage starts, thermal stress, unbalanced magnetic pulls, electromagnetic forces, noise, or manufacturing defects [8].

B.3 Phase unbalances and single phasing fault:

Phase unbalance occurs when the voltages between the three phases are unequal, leading to increased current in the motor winding, which can cause overheating and motor damage. Single phasing, the worst-case scenario of voltage unbalance, happens when one phase is open-circuited due to issues like loose connections or a blown fuse [9] [10]. This can result in overheating, shaft vibration, insulation damage, and ultimately, stator winding failures.

III. FAULT MONITORING OF INDUCTION MOTORS

This section reviews techniques for detecting and diagnosing faults in induction motors (IMs), which can result from issues in the stator, rotor, or bearings. These faults lead to symptoms like unbalanced air gaps, flux variations, torque and speed fluctuations, overheating, vibrations, efficiency loss, and irregular currents and voltages. Condition monitoring techniques include magnetic flux and air gap torque measurement, acoustic noise and thermal monitoring, partial discharge measurement, speed and power analysis, surge testing, chemical analysis, and vibration and current monitoring [10].

The magnetic flux method uses concentric search coils to monitor axial flux and detect turn-to-turn faults, BRB, and rotor eccentricity. Four symmetrically mounted coils can pinpoint fault locations but face installation challenges. Air-gap torque measures flux linkages and currents, sensitive to unbalanced voltages and defects. Acoustic noise monitoring, through microphones or sound level meters, detects air-gap

eccentricity and stator faults despite strong noise. Thermal monitoring with sensors assesses stator core and bearing temperatures, while thermal imaging identifies faults like SWF and misalignment [10]. The partial discharge (PD) method finds insulation faults due to imperfections, overheating, or manufacturing defects.

Instantaneous angular speed waveforms and power signature analysis diagnose specific faults like BRB. Surge testing and cooling gas methods check winding and insulation faults. Lubricating oil analysis detects bearing damage through wear particles, and vibration monitoring with accelerometers identifies mechanical faults like unbalanced or misaligned rotors and electrical faults such as BRB and SWF [11]. Machine current signature analysis (MCSA) is diagnoses electrical and some mechanical faults using current probes. The extended Park's vector approach analyzes SWF and bearing faults in current signals. Vibration and current monitoring are preferred for their non-intrusiveness, reliability, and cost-effectiveness, offering high accuracy for online fault detection. Signal processing in time, frequency, and time-frequency domains helps identify deviations caused by various IM faults.

A. Time domain analysis of IM faults:

Faults in induction motors (IMs) alter vibration and current signals over time, making it hard to distinguish between normal and faulty conditions. Bearing faults create impulse-like vibrations, while current signals, dominated by line frequency, obscure fault detection. Phase unbalance and stator winding faults cause noticeable current magnitude variations. Due to noise and imbalances, early fault detection via raw time-domain signals is challenging. Signal processing is needed to extract useful information [12]. Improved time-domain analysis includes band-pass filtering to isolate oscillations and angular data clustering to map these into discrete waveforms, with the amplitude of the fundamental harmonic indicating unbalance.

Further improvements involve extracting statistical features such as RMS value, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis from time-domain signals. Identifying the most sensitive features for specific faults remains challenging. Multiple statistical features are used to characterize and diagnose faults in IMs, often integrating with AI systems for better automation and accuracy [12] [13].

B. Frequency domain analysis of IM faults:

To illustrate the frequency domain analysis of induction motors (IMs), data was gathered from lab experiments.

Fig. 6 Test setup used for testing of an IM

The setup included an IM, a machine fault simulator (MFS), sensors (AC current probe, tri-axial accelerometer), a DC power source, a data acquisition system (DAQ), and a monitor. The MFS had a 0.373 kW, 50 Hz, 2-pole IM, with a sliding shaft, flexible coupling, split bracket bearing housing, and other components. The IM was connected to the shaft via a flexible coupling, with the shaft mounted on split bracket bearings. A pulley system linked the shaft to a gearbox and magnetic brake for load application. The VFD controlled motor speed, and a tachometer measured shaft speed, powered by a DC source. The simulator's base plate had vibration isolators and a base stiffener for adjustments.

Fig. 7 Turn fault of the IM

The test rig included motors with various faults: five conditions (broken rotor bar, bearing fault, unbalanced rotor, bowed rotor, misaligned rotor) in five motors, and four additional faults (stator winding faults SWF1, SWF2; phase unbalance PUF1, PUF2) in two motors. BRB defects were created by drilling rotor bars, while SWF faults were simulated with external loads [14]. A variable resistor controlled SWF fault severity. Similar faults, including BF, UR, BR, and MR, were also simulated. Frequency spectra of vibration and current signals reflecting these faults were analyzed using the collected frequency domain data.

B.1 Healthy motor:

An ideal healthy induction motor (IM) with no defects (ND) has symmetrical physical construction, including consistent air-gap length, equal rotor and stator resistances, and a balanced rotor. However, real-world IMs often have minor construction asymmetries, such as variable air-gap lengths and unequal winding resistances, which generate unequal magnetic flux and magnetic force-induced vibrations [15]. Consequently, even healthy IMs produce low-magnitude vibrations and variations in current signals.

The figure shows the power spectrum of the stator current of a healthy motor operating at 40 Hz under full load [15]. Despite a line current frequency of 50 Hz, the motor's current spectrum with ND peaks at 40 Hz due to the VFD supplying 40 Hz. Sidebands of lower amplitudes around the supply frequency are also present in healthy machines, possibly due to factors like uneven rotor bar resistance or rotor asymmetry. An increase in the amplitude and number of sidebands typically indicates faults.

B.2 Broken rotor bars:

A rotor bar can fail due to a variety of stresses, including thermal, magnetic, mechanical, dynamic, residual, and environmental stresses [16]. When rotor irregularity occurs due to a broken rotor bar, it produce

a backward rotating field in totaling to the forward rotating field, moving at a speed of $(-sf_s)$. This outcome in a supplementary frequency component $f_b = (1 - 2ks) f_s$ in the stator current. The cyclic dissimilarity in the current causes speed oscillation and torque pulsation at twice the slip frequency $(2sf_s)$, which in turn makes upper sideband components at $f_b = (1 \pm 2ks) f_s$, where $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k = 1, 2, 3 \dots n$.

Thus, broken rotor bars tend to induce supplementary apparatus in the stator current at frequencies given by $f_b = (1 \pm 2ks) f_s$.

Fig. 8 Power variety of stator current in healthy IM at T3 while VFD is situated with 40 Hz

When a bar in an induction motor (IM) is broken, and it disrupts the electromagnetic field, leading to unbalanced magnetic forces. This imbalance causes torque modulations and motor vibrations, which manifest as increased amplitudes at the rotational frequency and its sidebands in the vibration spectrum [16]. The disturbance rotates at the rotor's speed and modulates at the pole pass frequency, determined by the slip frequency and the number of poles.

$$f_{brb} = f_r \pm f_p \text{ (Where, } f_p = \text{ Pole pass frequency)}$$

To study the BRB fault, the stator current power spectra for the BRB at 40 Hz under full load is revealed. Sidebands appear around 40 Hz, not 50 Hz, because the VFD was set to 40 Hz. The slip at this speed and load is just about 4.29%, calculated by $S = (N_s - N_r) / N_s$. Where $N_s =$ Synchronous speed and $N_r =$ Rotor speed. Fault frequencies or sidebands are 37 Hz and 43 Hz for $k = 1$, 34 Hz and 46 Hz for $k = 2$, and 31 Hz and 49 Hz for $k = 3$. These sidebands are observable in the current spectrum, indicating broken bars.

B.3 Stator winding faults or armature faults:

Asymmetrical short circuits in the stator winding, often caused by insulation damage, result from hot spots in the stator core, leading to high temperatures, electrical discharges, structural loosening, moisture, and oil contamination [17]. The additional frequency components in the current spectrum due to this fault are given by,

$$f_{st} = \left[k \pm \frac{n(1-s)}{p} \right] f_s$$

Where f_{st} = short turn's frequency, f_s = supply frequency, p = number of pole pairs, $k = 1, 3, 5 \dots$ and $n = 1, 2 \dots$

To study the SWF, the stator current power spectrum of an IM with the SWF at 40 Hz under full load is shown in above figure. The slip at this speed and load is approximately 4.29%. The fault frequency take place at 78.5 Hz & 1.5 Hz ($k = 1$ & $n = 1$); 158.5 Hz and 81.5 Hz ($k = 3$ & $n = 3$); 238.5 Hz and 161.5 Hz ($k = 5$ & $n = 5$); 117 Hz ($k = 1$ & $n = 2$); and 155.5 Hz ($k = 1$ & $n = 3$). Over figure shows that fault frequencies are clearly visible, indicating the stator winding fault in the IM.

Fig. 9 Stator current power band of IM with the BRB at T3 while VFD is situated with 40 Hz

Fig. 10 Vibration or acceleration power band of IM with the BRB at T3 while VFD = 40 Hz

To study the SWF, the trembling range of an IM with the SWF at 40 Hz under full-load is shown in the figure below. Fault frequencies of 76.56 Hz, 153.12 Hz, and 306.24 Hz (calculated as pf_r ; $2pf_r$; $4pf_r$; ...) are observed in the trembling range.

B.4 Bearing faults:

Bearings, crucial to the IM, are prone to faults, including ball, outer race, inner race, and train defects. These faults cause vibrations at the component's rotational speed, with characteristic frequencies determined by rotational speed and bearing dimensions [18].

Fig. 11 Stator current power range of IM with the SWF at T3 while VFD = 40 Hz

Fig. 12 Vibration or acceleration power range of IM with the SWF at T3 while VFD = 40 Hz

Vibration analysis is used to sense these frequencies, through definite frequencies associated with every type of fault:

Inner race defects,

$$f_i = Z \frac{f_r}{2} \left(1 + \frac{d}{D} \cos \alpha \right)$$

Outer race defects,

$$f_o = Z \frac{f_r}{2} \left(1 - \frac{d}{D} \cos \alpha \right)$$

Ball defects,

$$f_b = Z \frac{f_r}{d} \left(1 - \frac{d^2}{D^2} \cos^2 \alpha \right)$$

And Train defects,

$$f_t = \frac{f_r^2}{2} \left(1 - \frac{d}{D} \cos \alpha \right)$$

For bearings with 6–12 balls, the characteristic apparatus are estimated by $f_o = 0.4 Z f_r$ and $f_i = 0.6 Z f_r$, where Z is the number of rollers/balls, and f_r is the rotational frequency. The harmonic apparatus generated by BF in the current spectrum are described by,

$$f_{bg} = [f_s \pm k f_v]$$

Here, $k = 1, 2$, and so on (f_v denotes one of the vibration characteristic frequencies). The analysis of the NSK 6203 bearing with a 29 mm pitch diameter, 6.75 mm rolling element diameter, and 8 rolling elements at a rotor speed of 2341 rpm (39.02 Hz) reveals a characteristic outer race frequency of 119.60 Hz.

Fig. 13 Vibration or acceleration power range of IM with the BF at T3 while VFD = 40 Hz

The vibration spectrum under fault conditions clearly shows this frequency and its harmonics (239.2 Hz, 358.05 Hz, and 478.43 Hz), as well as the characteristic fault frequency of 76.60 Hz and other significant frequencies: 159.6 Hz, 199.20 Hz, 279.20 Hz, 318.20 Hz, and 398.80 Hz.

B.5 Air-gap eccentricity related fault:

Air gap eccentricity, the uneven distance between rotor and stator, causes an unbalanced force that displaces the rotor from the stator core. Static eccentricity causes a steady pull, while dynamic eccentricity creates a varying magnetic pull at the rotor's angular velocity. This eccentricity introduces extra frequencies in current and vibration spectra, with the characteristic frequency in the current spectrum given by,

$$f_{ect} = \left[1 \pm \frac{m(1-s)}{p} \right] f_s$$

To detect air-gap eccentricity in an induction motor (IM), a bowed rotor bar (BRB) is analyzed, revealing characteristic fault frequencies in the current spectrum at 79.01 Hz, 118.02 Hz, 157.03 Hz, and 196.04 Hz.

Fig. 14 Stator current power range of IM with the BF at T3 while VFD = 40 Hz

Here, methods like higher-order spectra and the Hilbert transform enhance current and vibration monitoring. Bi-spectrum analysis is particularly useful for detecting faults such as asymmetrical issues and mechanical bearing movement, providing more detail than power spectrum analysis. Combining current and vibration analyses improves fault diagnosis; though estimating characteristic frequencies in complex systems remains challenging due to load variability and noise.

Fig. 15 Stator current power range of IM with the BRB at T3 while VFD = 40 Hz

The Fourier and Hilbert transforms detect BRB under various conditions, with HT effectively identifying BRB frequencies at low slip [20].

B.6 Challenges in the time, frequency analyses of vibration and current signals for IM faults:

Fault identification in induction motors (IMs) cannot rely only on time-domain vibration and current signals, as faults are often masked by the supply frequency. While spectrum analysis can help when speed oscillations are minimal, accuracy depends on signal-to-noise ratio, sampling rate, and frequency resolution.

High sampling rates and resolution are needed to capture fault signatures, but balancing these can be challenging in complex systems.

B.7 Advanced condition monitoring methods for IM faults:

Researchers have tackled fault detection using various methods. For example, a MUSIC algorithm analyzed fault frequencies for bearing faults, while extended-Kalman filters with FFT improved BRB fault detection by estimating rotor resistance. A Rayleigh quotient-based estimator offered high accuracy with low complexity for BRB faults, and wavelet transform analysis enhanced induction motor fault detection by examining vibration signals across frequency ranges [20].

Various fault detection methods, including power spectrum graphs and wavelet scalograms, face issues with complexity and cost [20]. Conventional signal-based methods can be unreliable due to changing motor conditions, while mathematical modeling relies on residuals for fault detection. AI-based techniques enhance performance by reducing human intervention and avoiding detailed motor models through data-driven approaches.

IV. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED FAULT DIAGNOSIS OF IMs

The AI-based diagnostic system uses signal-based methods and classification tools, including Neural Networks, Fuzzy Logic, Genetic Algorithms, Hidden Markov Models, Bayesian classifiers, Support Vector Machines, and Deep Learning algorithms [21].

A. ANN based diagnosis:

TANN is commonly used for fault diagnosis in induction motors (IMs). A neural network-based incipient fault detector for small and medium IMs simplifies detection using stator current and rotor speed, overcoming traditional challenges. Integrating FFT with ANN enhances fault detection, including BRB, through MCSA, without needing extra motor or load data [22]. This method employs time-frequency spectrum analysis to extract current signatures, improving torque recognition and anomaly interpretation [22].

B. Fuzzy logic based diagnosis:

Fuzzy logic (FL) is applied in diagnosing induction motor (IM) faults and has been enhanced by integrating neural networks (NN) for improved detection [23]. Neural fuzzy systems like FALCON and ANFIS have proven effective in detecting early-stage faults. FL techniques preprocess vibration signals using higher-order statistics and FFT to analyze fault frequencies. AI methods, including NN and FL, face challenges like spectral leakage at low motor slip [23]. FL also uses fuzzy subsets and membership functions to describe stator current amplitudes for IM condition diagnosis.

C. Other hybrid AI method based diagnosis:

IM fault diagnosis methods like ANN, FL, and SVM have limitations, leading to ongoing research into hybrid and novel AI approaches. Promising methods include the wise minimum error for BRB using Park's transformation, HMM for SWF and BRB, and the combination of LDA and PCA, which is more robust under noisy conditions [24]. Gaussian mixture models, Bayesian maximum models with envelope analysis, and Bayesian-Gaussian mixture models with Fisher's linear discriminate analysis effectively diagnose BRB, SWF, air-gap eccentricity, and load levels [25].

D. New challenges in AI based fault diagnosis:

Over the past two decades, researchers have explored various intelligent systems like ANN, fuzzy logic, neuro-fuzzy, and GA for IM fault diagnosis, though SVM remains underutilized in this area. There is significant potential for hybrid AI techniques in future fault monitoring and diagnosis. One major challenge in AI-based systems is the consistency of training and testing data, as training typically uses historical industry data, while testing relies on real-time measurements [26]. Another common issue is the reliance on laboratory-acquired signals, which, although effective due to controlled conditions, may not generalize well in real-world scenarios.

These extracted features help represent each IM fault, forming distinct clusters in feature space that enhance diagnosis. Generalization is particularly challenging in AI systems due to high variance and limited information, requiring thorough signal preprocessing for broader applicability. Effective fault diagnosis in industrial settings depends on identifying and normalizing crucial system-specific features to improve generalization [27]. Optimizing input parameters is key to accurate fault prediction, and evaluating classifier performance under varying conditions can enhance system adaptability. This paper reviews recent developments in AI-based condition monitoring for IM fault detection, summarizing the findings in the next section, with all reviewed papers listed below.

TABLE 1

A SEQUENTIAL REVIEW OF THE PAPERS SET ON AI PEDESTAL FAULT ANALYSIS OF IM

Reference	Type of Fault in IM	Methodology	Observation
28	BRB, Eccentricity & SWF	Fuzzy Logic	95 % Accuracy
29	Single phasing, locked rotor and ground fault	ANN Method	92 % Accuracy
30	BRB, BF & SWF	Multilayer perception network or NN	93 % Accuracy
31	Mechanical unbalance, misalignment, BF & SWF	ART-KNN	97 % Accuracy
32	BRB & SWF	Hidden Markov Model	89 % Accuracy
33	Bearing and inter-turn insulation faults	ANFIS	Good Performance
34	SWF, BRB, BF & air gap eccentricity	SVM Method	Better performance with nonlinear feature
35	BF, UR & MR	ANN and SVM	More Reliable
36	Multiple combined faults	Fuzzy logic inference	Better narration
37	BRB, BF, BR, UR and PUF	Fuzzy logic and ANN	Significantly Effective
38	BF & Eccentricity	QDA and SVM	94.5 % accuracy

39	BRB, SWF, BF	SVM & ANN	Appropriate for all
40	UR, BF, UR & BRB	ENN	Better Performance
41	SWF & BF	BNN & ANN	Effective & Accurate

V. RESEARCH GAPS & INSPIRATIONS FOR UPCOMING RESEARCH WORK

The literature on fault discovery and analysis of induction motors (IMs) reveals several key interpretations:

- A. Significance of IMs:** IMs are critical to industrial processes, prompting significant efforts for their monitoring and early fault detection to prevent unscheduled maintenance and breakdowns.
- B. Fault Types:** Common faults include bearing, stator winding, broken rotor, rotor-related, and phase unbalance faults. Combined studies of these faults and their severity are rare.
- C. Investigative Techniques:** Techniques like MCSA, vibration analysis, electromagnetic torque measurement, acoustic analysis, and thermal analysis are used, with vibration signature analysis and MCSA being the most popular due to their accuracy and reliability.
- D. Fault Exposure:** Research typically focuses on two to three fault types in different IMs. Comprehensive diagnosis of all possible mechanical and electrical faults is necessary to prevent further damage.
- E. Severity Levels:** Considering faults under progression to detect them at an early stage is crucial, but this is rarely addressed in the literature. A robust methodology to classify various fault conditions and severity levels is needed.
- F. Single System Diagnosis:** A fault detection system for simultaneous faults in multiple IMs of the same kind is lacking.
- G. AI Methods:** Advances from conventional to AI methods for fault detection present research opportunities. AI diagnostic systems face challenges in efficiency, reliability, computational time, database sufficiency, and robustness.
- H. SVM Use:** SVM is frequently used for fault diagnosis due to its accuracy and efficiency. Multi-fault diagnosis in IMs using SVM is still uncommon.
- I. Sampling Frequency:** Higher sampling frequencies are used in AI-based fault detection. Optimized sampling frequency and data points can improve diagnostic time and reduce costs.
- J. Feature Extraction:** AI for fault diagnosis involves preprocessing, feature extraction, selection of AI parameters, and recognition. Identifying significant features and appropriate tools for specific problems is challenging.
- K. Signal Processing:** Time, frequency, and advanced time-frequency methods like wavelets are used for fault feature extraction. Combining wavelets with AI methods like SVM and deep learning for IM fault diagnosis needs further exploration.
- L. Wavelet Selection:** Despite extensive studies on wavelets, choosing the appropriate mother wavelet and its features for intelligent fault diagnosis remains an open issue.
- M. Operational Conditions:** Diagnosing faults under varying operational conditions, especially at light loads, is difficult. Rotor speed fluctuations during data acquisition under different loads can reduce diagnostic accuracy.
- N. Database Limitations:** AI systems often rely on symptoms databases, but these may not cover all operational conditions. Fault diagnosis becomes challenging when test data don't match the training database.
- O. Generalization:** Testing AI algorithms with data from different IM configurations and using normalized signal features can aid generalization.

- P. Numerical Models:** Using training data from numerical models and testing data from experimental measurements is challenging due to the difficulty in creating accurate models for each fault.
- Q. Simultaneous Faults:** Studying the impact of simultaneous faults on AI-based diagnostics can provide insights.
- R. Combined Systems:** Fault diagnosis of combined rotating systems (e.g., IM with a pump or gearbox) using measurements from one location can be explored.
- S. Practical Constraints:** Applying AI methodologies in real industry setups with limited system signals is a practical challenge that needs addressing.

VI. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper reviews recent advancements in fault detection and diagnosis techniques for induction motors (IMs), focusing on various electrical and mechanical faults. We provide a comprehensive analysis of these techniques, highlighting their strengths and limitations. Additionally, we explore the growing field of AI-based fault diagnosis methods, which offer significant advantages over traditional signal-based approaches. Despite their promise, AI-based condition monitoring and fault diagnosis for IMs still face challenges and require further research. A key issue in machine learning is generalization, which is crucial for accurately predicting outcomes for new, unseen inputs, especially in cases characterized by high variance and limited information.

REFERENCES

- [1] Choudhary, A., Goyal, D., Shimi, S. L., & Akula, A. (2019). Condition monitoring and fault diagnosis of induction motors: A review. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 26(4), 1221-1238.
- [2] Sobhi, S., Reshadi, M., Zarft, N., Terheide, A., & Dick, S. (2023). Condition monitoring and fault detection in small induction motors using machine learning algorithms. *Information*, 14(6), 329.
- [3] Sheikh, M. A., Bakhsh, S. T., Irfan, M., Nor, N. B. M., & Nowakowski, G. (2022). A review to diagnose faults related to three-phase industrial induction motors. *Journal of Failure Analysis and prevention*, 22(4), 1546-1557.
- [4] Almounajjed, A., Sahoo, A. K., Kumar, M. K., & Assaf, T. (2022). Fault diagnosis and investigation techniques for induction motor. *International Journal of Ambient Energy*, 43(1), 6341-6361.
- [5] Glowacz, A. (2023). Thermographic fault diagnosis of electrical faults of commutator and induction motors. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 121, 105962.
- [6] Terron-Santiago, C., Martinez-Roman, J., Puche-Panadero, R., & Sapena-Bano, A. (2021). A review of techniques used for induction machine fault modelling. *Sensors*, 21(14), 4855.
- [7] Sunal, C. E., Dyo, V., & Velisavljevic, V. (2022). Review of machine learning based fault detection for centrifugal pump induction motors. *IEEE access*, 10, 71344-71355.
- [8] Tran, M. Q., Liu, M. K., Tran, Q. V., & Nguyen, T. K. (2021). Effective fault diagnosis based on wavelet and convolutional attention neural network for induction motors. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 71, 1-13.
- [9] Hussein, A. M., Obed, A. A., Zubo, R. H., Al-Yasir, Y. I., Saleh, A. L., Fadhel, H., ... & Abd-Alhameed, R. A. (2022). Detection and Diagnosis of Stator and Rotor Electrical Faults for Three-Phase Induction Motor via Wavelet Energy Approach. *Electronics*, 11(8), 1253.
- [10] Sanchez, O. D., Martinez-Soltero, G., Alvarez, J. G., & Alanis, A. Y. (2023). Real-Time neural classifiers for sensor faults in three phase induction motors. *IEEE Access*, 11, 19657-19668.
- [11] Agahi, H., & Mahmoodzadeh, A. (2020). Decision fusion scheme for bearing defects diagnosis in induction motors. *Electrical Engineering*, 102(4), 2269-2279.

- [12] Brusamarello, B., Da Silva, J. C. C., de Morais Sousa, K., & Guarneri, G. A. (2022). Bearing fault detection in three-phase induction motors using support vector machine and fiber Bragg grating. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 23(5), 4413-4421.
- [13] Carbonieri, M., Di Leonardo, L., Tursini, M., Villani, M., & Popescu, M. (2020, October). Induction motor performance prediction using static FEA: Method description and comparison with time-domain approach. In *2020 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)* (pp. 1351-1356). IEEE.
- [14] Misra, S., Kumar, S., Sayyad, S., Bongale, A., Jadhav, P., Kotecha, K., & Gabralla, L. A. (2022). Fault detection in induction motor using time domain and spectral imaging-based transfer learning approach on vibration data. *Sensors*, 22(21), 8210.
- [15] Sunal, C. E., Dyo, V., & Velisavljevic, V. (2022). Review of machine learning based fault detection for centrifugal pump induction motors. *IEEE access*, 10, 71344-71355.
- [16] Ferrucho-Alvarez, E. R., Martinez-Herrera, A. L., Cabal-Yepe, E., Rodriguez-Donate, C., Lopez-Ramirez, M., & Mata-Chavez, R. I. (2021). Broken rotor bar detection in induction motors through contrast estimation. *Sensors*, 21(22), 7446.
- [17] Sheikh, M. A., Bakhsh, S. T., Irfan, M., Nor, N. B. M., & Nowakowski, G. (2022). A review to diagnose faults related to three-phase industrial induction motors. *Journal of Failure Analysis and prevention*, 22(4), 1546-1557.
- [18] Toma, R. N., Piltan, F., & Kim, J. M. (2021). A deep autoencoder-based convolution neural network framework for bearing fault classification in induction motors. *Sensors*, 21(24), 8453.
- [19] Faiz, J., Ghods, M., & Tajdini, A. (2020). Dynamic air gap asymmetry fault detection in single-sided linear induction motors. *IET Electric Power Applications*, 14(4), 605-613.
- [20] Malik, H., Iqbal, A., & Yadav, A. K. (2020). *Soft computing in condition monitoring and diagnostics of electrical and mechanical systems* (Vol. 1096, p. 499). Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany: Springer.
- [21] Kumar, P., & Hati, A. S. (2021). Review on machine learning algorithm based fault detection in induction motors. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 28(3), 1929-1940.
- [22] Salih, I. H., & Loganathan, G. B. (2020). Induction motor fault monitoring and fault classification using deep learning probabilistic neural network. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6), 2196-2213.
- [23] Namdar, A., Samet, H., Allahbakhshi, M., Tajdinian, M., & Ghanbari, T. (2022). A robust stator inter-turn fault detection in induction motor utilizing Kalman filter-based algorithm. *Measurement*, 187, 110181.
- [24] AlShorman, O., Irfan, M., Saad, N., Zhen, D., Haider, N., Glowacz, A., & AlShorman, A. (2020). A review of artificial intelligence methods for condition monitoring and fault diagnosis of rolling element bearings for induction motor. *Shock and vibration*, 2020(1), 8843759.
- [25] Brito, L. C., Susto, G. A., Brito, J. N., & Duarte, M. A. (2022). An explainable artificial intelligence approach for unsupervised fault detection and diagnosis in rotating machinery. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 163, 108105.
- [26] Li, J., Huang, R., He, G., Liao, Y., Wang, Z., & Li, W. (2020). A two-stage transfer adversarial network for intelligent fault diagnosis of rotating machinery with multiple new faults. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, 26(3), 1591-1601.
- [27] Polenghi, A., Cattaneo, L., & Macchi, M. (2024). A framework for fault detection and diagnostics of articulated collaborative robots based on hybrid series modelling of Artificial Intelligence algorithms. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 35(5), 1929-1947.
- [28] Akar, M., & Gercekcioglu, H. S. (2017). Instantaneous power factor signature analysis for efficient fault diagnosis in inverter fed three phased induction motors. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 42(12), 8338-8345.
- [29] Alsaedi, M. A. (2015). Fault diagnosis of three-phase induction motor: A review. *Optics*, 4(1), 1-8.

- [30] Amezquita-Sanchez, J. P., Valtierra-Rodriguez, M., Perez-Ramirez, C. A., Camarena-Martinez, D., Garcia-Perez, A., & Romero-Troncoso, R. J. (2017). Fractal dimension and fuzzy logic systems for broken rotor bar detection in induction motors at start-up and steady-state regimes. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 28(7), 075001.
- [31] Antonino-Daviu, J., Jover, P., Riera, M., Arkkio, A., & Roger-Folch, J. (2007). DWT analysis of numerical and experimental data for the diagnosis of dynamic eccentricities in induction motors. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 21(6), 2575-2589.
- [32] Baccarini, L. M. R., e Silva, V. V. R., de Menezes, B. R., & Caminhas, W. M. (2011). SVM practical industrial application for mechanical faults diagnostic. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 38(6), 6980-6984.
- [33] Bandyopadhyay, I., Purkait, P., & Koley, C. (2016). A combined image processing and Nearest Neighbor Algorithm tool for classification of incipient faults in induction motor drives. *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 54, 296-312.
- [34] Bellini, A., Filippetti, F., Franceschini, G., Tassoni, C., & Kliman, G. B. (2001). Quantitative evaluation of induction motor broken bars by means of electrical signature analysis. *IEEE Transactions on industry applications*, 37(5), 1248-1255.
- [35] Bonnett, A. H., & Soukup, G. C. (1988). Analysis of rotor failures in squirrel-cage induction motors. *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, 24(6), 1124-1130.
- [36] Cheng, F., Qu, L., & Qiao, W. (2017). Fault prognosis and remaining useful life prediction of wind turbine gearboxes using current signal analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, 9(1), 157-167.
- [37] Culbert, I. M., & Rhodes, W. (2007). Notice of violation of IEEE publication principles: using current signature analysis technology to reliably detect cage winding defects in squirrel-cage induction motors. *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, 43(2), 422-428.
- [38] Douglas, H., Pillay, P., & Ziarani, A. K. (2004). A new algorithm for transient motor current signature analysis using wavelets. *IEEE Transactions on industry applications*, 40(5), 1361-1368.
- [39] Fiser, R., & Ferkoj, S. (2001). Application of a finite element method to predict damaged induction motor performance. *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 37(5), 3635-3639.
- [40] Gangsar, P., & Tiwari, R. (2019). A support vector machine based fault diagnostics of Induction motors for practical situation of multi-sensor limited data case. *Measurement*, 135, 694-711.
- [41] Günal, S., & Gerek, Ö. N. (2009). Induction machine condition monitoring using notch-filtered motor current. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 23(8), 2658-2670.